

An Interpretation of Maxwell-Boltzmann, Tsallis Entropy

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In (1), we tried to link entropy to a sum of functions $p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ such that $h(p(e_i)) = f(e_i) (-1/T)$, where $f(e_i)$ is linked to the conserved quantity (i.e. constraint in a maximization problem). It is usually e_i . (In the Tsallis case, $p(e_i)$ power q is used instead of $p(e_i)$.) We applied these ideas to the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Tsallis and Kaniadakis scenarios.

Here, we wish to consider only the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis cases, and try to interpret entropy in the following manner. We begin with the two constraints: $\sum_i f(e_i) p(e_i) = F$ and $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$. In other words, one has two conserved quantities and the relations: $\sum_i f(e_i) dp(e_i) = 0$ ((1a)) and $\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$ ((1b)).

We note that there may be many sets $\{p(e_i)\}$ which satisfy the two constraints. This begs the question: Which set of $p(e_i)$ appears in nature. We try to argue that only one set appears and it is one for which a special unknown function, called entropy or lack of information, when maximized, minimizes information, a goal of a statistical treatment. It cannot, however, eliminate the information of the two a priori constraints.

The simplest way to create such a function is to make use of the two relations because maximizing an entropy function $G(p(e_i))$'s means that $G(p(e_i)) = G(p(e_i) + dp(e_i))$ to first order. Given that there are two constraints and that they are written in terms of a sum over i terms, one may define: $G = \sum_i A(p(e_i)) B(p(e_i))$.

$$dG=0 = \sum_i dA/dp(e_i) B dp(e_i) + \sum_i A dB/dp(e_i) dp(e_i)$$

Having the above match the equation ((1a)) and ((1b)), leads to a math solution for A and B and hence G , the entropy and respects the constraints. No other information is used, which means one is dealing with minimal information aside from the constraints. (This holds for the MB and Tsallis cases, but in (1), we argued that the Kaniadakis case is more complicated.)

Why Should One Have An Entropy Function in the First Place?

Consider the two constraints:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i f(e_i) p(e_i) = F \quad ((2b)) \quad (\text{or } \sum_i f(e_i) p(e_i) \text{ power } q \text{ in the Tsallis case})$$

$f(e_i)$ is usually e_i and $F=E$ (total energy)

These constraints represent conserved quantities which are linked to particles, i.e. each particle is linked with a probability and e_i value.

Given ((2a)), ((2b)), one may immediately write ((1a)), ((1b)), i.e.

$$\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i f(e_i) dp(e_i) = 0$$

The point is that mathematically one may write:

$$G = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } A(p(e_i)) B(p(e_i)) \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{Then: } dG = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } A(p(e_i)) dB/dp(e_i) dp(e_i) + \text{Sum over } i \text{ } B dA/dp(e_i) dp(e_i) \quad ((4))$$

One may choose to have the first sum term on the RHS match ((1a)) and the second, ((1b)). In such a way, the constraints ((2a)) and ((2b)) are respected, and one has maximized a function G based on these two constraints and no other information

The question is: Why would one perform such a mathematical operation?

We note that there may be several sets of $\{ p(e_i) \}$ which satisfy the constraints ((2a)) and ((2b)). The question then becomes: Which set appears in nature? One would expect only one to be present. We argue that one wishes to have a set which minimizes the amount of information, keeping only the constraint information ((2a)) and ((2b)). We argue that this is exactly what the math function G in ((3)) does. In other words, one does not need to think in terms of factorials and maximizing arrangements. We argue that one only needs to minimize information keeping ((2a)) and ((2b)). Thus, G is the required entropy function. One must now solve for A(p(e_i)) and B(p(e_i)).

If $A(p(e_i)) = p(e_i)$ in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case and $p(e_i)$ power q in the Tsallis case, then:

$$B(e_i) = -1/T f(e_i) \quad (\text{where } -1/T \text{ is a constant}) \quad ((5a)) \quad \text{and}$$

$$p(e_i) dA/dp(e_i) = \text{constant} \quad (p(e_i) \text{ power } q \quad dA/dp(e_i) = \text{constant in the Tsallis case}) \quad ((5))$$

((4a)) and ((4b)) are sufficient to derive the MB and Tsallis distributions.

We first note that A(p(e)) is the inverse function of p(e_i) if p(e_i) is written as a function of the conserved/constraint $f(e_i)/T$. The key then to solving for the distribution is ((5b)).

In the MB case, $A = \ln(p(e_i))$ for $f(e_i) = e_i$ and in the Tsallis case:

$$A = c_1 + c_2 p(e_i) \text{ power } (1-q) \quad ((6))$$

One may then apply appropriate normalization conditions and argue that for $q=1$, A Tsallis should yield the MB A value, i.e $\ln(p(e_i))$.

Kaniadakis Case

In the Kaniadakis case, one keeps the form ((7)), but does not apply the condition $\text{sum over } i \text{ } dp(e_i) = 0$ to:

$$\sum_i A(p(e_i)) \frac{dB}{dp(e_i)} dp(e_i) = 0 \quad ((8a))$$

On the other hand: $\sum_i \frac{dA}{dp(e_i)} B dp(e_i)$ is mapped to $\sum_i f(e_i) p(e_i) = 0$.
 ((8b))

This means that: $A(p(e_i)) = f(e_i)(-1/T)$ as in the MB and Tsallis cases, but the $A(p(e_i))$ and $B(p(e_i))$ forms only need to satisfy ((8a)) and ((8b)).

Kaniadakis has shown that $A = p(e_i)$ and $B = \{p(e_i)^k - p(e_i)^{-k}\} / (2k)$ apply, but this means that ((8a)) yields:

$$\sum_i .5 \{ p(e_i)^k + p(e_i)^{-k} \} = 0 \quad ((9))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to show mathematically that given two constraints: $\sum_i f(e_i) p(e_i) = F$ (or $\sum_i f(e_i) p(e_i)^q$ for the Tsallis case) and $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$, the ensuing equations: $\sum_i f(e_i) dp(e_i) = 0$ (and the Tsallis case) and $\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$ allow one to create a function $G = \sum_i A(p(e_i)) B(p(e_i))$ (two factors for two constraints) such that: $dG = \sum_i \frac{dA}{dp(e_i)} B dp(e_i) + \sum_i A(p(e_i)) \frac{dB}{dp(e_i)} dp(e_i) = 0$. If one argues that the only information present is the two constraints, then one may mathematically set the first sum to $\sum_i f(e_i) dp(e_i) = 0$ and the second to $\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$. This approach works for the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis cases because one only needs to minimize information (hence the G or entropy function) such that the only information necessary is the constraint information. One does not need to think in terms of factorials and arrangements. The Kaniadakis case is a little more complicated because one does not use $\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$, but has a different result: $\sum_i \{ p(e_i)^k + p(e_i)^{-k} \} = 0$, which seems like extra information.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Underlying Meaning of Probability in Maxwell-Boltzmann, Tsallis and Kaniadakis Entropies (preprint, zenodo, 2025)